

Polarographic Investigations on the Kinetics of Discharge of Pb(II), Cd(II) and Tl(I) at D.M.E. in Aqueous Mixtures of Formamide and Dimethylformamide

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The reduction of Pb(II), Cd(II) and Tl(I) has been studied in aqueous mixtures of formamide and dimethylformamide. The general polarographic characteristics have been determined using 0.1M NaNO₃ as the supporting electrolyte. The reduction of Pb(II), Cd(II) and Tl(I) in the presence of these organic solvents has been found to be irreversible and diffusion controlled. Kinetics of the electrode reaction has been investigated and the values of kinetic parameters (transfer coefficient, αn_a and forward rate constant $k^0_{f,h}$) have been calculated by Koutecky's theoretical treatment as extended by Meites and Israel. The electrocapillary curves in the presence of these solvents have also been studied.

HALE and Parsons¹ studied the changes in i_d and $E_{1/2}$ of Cd(II), Pb(II) and Tl(I) in both purely non-aqueous formamide, methylformamide and dimethylformamide as well as in their aqueous mixtures. They determined $E_{1/2}$ values against a mercury pool as reference electrode.

In spite of the qualitative study of the polarographic behaviour of these cations in aqueous formamide and substituted formamide, the fact remains that a detailed quantitative study of the kinetics of electrode reaction of these cations in the presence of aqueous mixtures of formamide and dimethylformamide is lacking. With this aim in view, the kinetics of the discharge of Pb(II), Cd(II) and Tl(I) at d.m.e. has been undertaken employing Koutecky's² method as extended by Meites and Israel³.

Experimental

CdCl₂, Pb(NO₃)₂, Tl₂SO₄ were of either Analar, B.D.H. grade or Merck's guaranteed extra pure reagents. Their solutions were prepared in doubly distilled air free conductivity water. Triton X-100 (0.002%) was used as maximum suppressor. 0.1M NaNO₃ was used as the supporting electrolyte.

Polarographic measurements were performed with a manual polarograph (Toshniwal, CLO₂) in conjunction with Toshniwal polyflex galvanometer (PL 50). Saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.) was used as a reference electrode. All the measurements were performed at 25° ± 0.1°.

The d.m.e. had the following characteristics :

$$m = 3.144 \text{ mg/sec.}$$

$$t = 3.26 \text{ sec. (in open circuit)}$$

$$m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.610 \text{ mg}^{2/3}\text{sec}^{-1/2}$$

$$h_{corr} = 64.5 \text{ cm.}$$

But for Cd(II) in the presence of formamide the capillary characteristics were :

$$m = 1.50 \text{ mg/sec.}$$

$$t = 4.04 \text{ sec. (in open circuit)}$$

$$m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 1.654 \text{ mg}^{2/3}\text{sec}^{-1/2}$$

$$h_{corr} = 64.5 \text{ cm.}$$

Purified hydrogen was used for removing dissolved oxygen. The gas presaturated with water vapour was passed through a solution having the same composition as that of the experimental mixture.

Logarithmic plots of a series of C-V curves determined for Pb(II), Cd(II) and Tl(I) in the presence of different percentages of aqueous mixtures of formamide and dimethylformamide yielded straight lines with different slopes deviating considerably from the theoretical value expected for one or two electron reductions and thus revealing the irreversible nature of the waves.

Throughout the measurements, the current at the end of the drop life was recorded instead of the average current because the determination of kinetic parameters is based on the Koutecky's calculations which are more accurately reproduced by measuring the maximum current⁴. The kinetic parameters (transfer coefficient αn_a and the forward rate constant $k^0_{f,h}$) have been calculated by Koutecky's² treatment as extended by Meites and Israel³.

Results and Discussion

Cd(II), Pb(II) and Tl(I) give a single well defined wave in aqueous as well as in the presence of aqueous mixtures of formamide and dimethylformamide (Representative Figures 1 and 2). The plots of

 Fig. 1. Polarograms of 1 mM Tl⁺ in 0.1 M NaNO₃ at different percentages of formamide.

 Fig. 2. Polarograms of 1 mM Tl⁺ in 0.1M NaNO₃ at different percentages of dimethylformamide.

i_d vs. square root of the height of the mercury column and of concentration have been found to be linear indicating that the reduction of Cd(II), Pb(II) and Tl(I) in the presence of aqueous mixtures of these organic solvents is diffusion controlled (Representative Figure 3a and b).

The kinetic parameters (the transfer coefficient αn_a and the rate constant $k_{f,h}^0$ at -0.2412 vs. S.C.E.) have been calculated by Koutecky's treatment as extended by Meites and Israel, which is based on a plot of $E_{d,e}$ vs. $\log i/i_d - i$ and may be constructed as for a reversible wave.

The mathematical solution for an electrode reaction at the d.m.e. controlled by the kinetics of the electron transfer is given by

$$i/i_d = F(X) \quad \dots (1)$$

where

$$X = \left(\frac{12}{7}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} k_{f,h} \frac{t^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_0^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad \dots (2)$$

in which 't' is drop time, D_0 is the diffusion coefficient of electro-active substance, $k_{f,h}^0$ is the potential dependent heterogeneous rate constant described by

$$k_{f,h} = k_{f,h}^0 \exp[-\alpha n_a F(E + 0.2412)/RT] \quad \dots (3)$$

where E is referred to C.S.E., 'i' and ' i_d ' are the currents that actually flow at the end of the life of the drop at potential E and on the plateau of the wave respectively. From the values of i/i_d at various selected potentials, the corresponding values of 'X' may be obtained from the original table of Koutecky².

Fig. 3. (a) i_d Vs $\sqrt{h_{corr}}$ plots of Tl^+ in the presence 60% formamide and 60% dimethylformamide.

Fig. 3. (b) i_d Vs C plots of Tl^+ in the presence of 50% formamide and 50% dimethylformamide.

Combining equation (3) with equation (2), we get with

$$\log X = \log(12/7)^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \frac{k_{f,h}^0 h t^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_0^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{\alpha n_a F(E + 0.24'2)}{2.303RT} \dots (4)$$

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = -0.2412 + \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{1.349 k_{f,h}^0 h t^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_0^{\frac{1}{2}}} \dots (8)$$

Thus a plot of $\log X$ vs $E_{d.e}$ shall be linear, at $E = 0$ (vs N.H.E. or -0.2412 vs S.C.E.) the value of $k_{f,h}^0$ can be obtained. Meanwhile αn_a is obtained from the slope of the line.

In these equations both $E_{d.e}$ and $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ are referred to the S.C.E.

The amount of labour involved in the process is excessive. Meites and Israel³ have shown that the labour can be considerably decreased by taking advantage of the fact that, for value of i/i_d between 0.1 to 0.95, Koutecky's values for X and $F(X)$ correspond to a linear relationship between $\log X$ and $\log\{F(X)/[1-F(X)]\}$. This is given by the equation :

The kinetic parameters were calculated using equations (7) and (8). The value of αn_a was obtained

from the slope = $-\frac{(0.0542)}{\alpha n_a}$ of the straight line of

$E_{d.e}$ vs $\log i/(i_d - i)$ (Representative Fig. 4). The intercept of the same plot gave the value of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$,

$$\log X = -0.0130 + 0.9163 \log \frac{F(X)}{1-F(X)}$$

which becomes on introducing $F(X) = i/i_d$.

$$\log X = -0.0130 + 0.9163 \log \frac{i}{i_d - i} \dots (5)$$

combining this with equation (4), the equation for a irreversible wave becomes at 25° :

$$E_{d.e} + 0.2412 = \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{1.349 k_{f,h}^0 h t^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_0^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{i}{i_d - i} \dots (6)$$

which may be written as

$$E_{d.e} = E_{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{i}{i_d - i} \dots (7)$$

Fig. 4. $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ Vs. $E_{d.e}$ plots of Pb^{2+} at different percentages of formamide.

which was used to calculate $k_{f,h}^0$ after having the value of $D_0^{\frac{1}{2}}$ from the Ilkovic equation. The values of αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ calculated at different percentages of formamide and dimethylformamide are tabulated in the following tables:

From Tables 1, 2 and 3 it is clear that with the gradual increase in the percentage of formamide, the diffusion coefficient of the ions Pb(II), Cd(II) and Tl(I) is decreased and hence the diffusion current ' i_d ' shows a regular decrease. Viscosity however

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS OF 1 mM Pb(II) IN 0.1M NaNO₃ IN THE PRESENCE OF FORMAMIDE AND DIMETHYLFORMAMIDE.

Percentage solvent by Vol.	i_d μA	Slope V	$\frac{-E_{\frac{1}{2}}}{V}$ S.C.E.	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² /sec	η Centipoise	$i_d \eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$	αn_a	$k_{f,h}^0$
<i>Formamide</i>								
0	10.208	0.0306	0.402	7.663	0.8919	9.414	—	—
10	10.120	0.0487	0.437	7.541	0.9170	9.694	1.1110	1.954×10^{-7}
20	9.856	0.0476	0.463	7.155	0.9977	9.840	1.1384	5.951×10^{-8}
30	9.592	0.0454	0.495	6.776	1.0960	10.090	1.1925	8.453×10^{-9}
40	9.152	0.0465	0.516	6.169	1.1900	9.989	1.1655	4.925×10^{-9}
50	8.448	0.0444	0.520	5.255	1.3510	9.809	1.2207	1.671×10^{-9}
60	7.964	0.0425	0.540	4.671	1.6020	9.772	1.2752	3.207×10^{-10}
70	7.216	0.0416	0.660	3.835	1.9050	9.759	1.3029	8.016×10^{-11}
80	6.688	0.0370	0.543	3.295	2.1080	9.677	1.4658	2.428×10^{-11}
<i>Dimethylformamide</i>								
0	10.208	0.0306	0.402	7.663	0.8919	9.414	—	—
10	9.328	0.0434	0.407	6.410	1.0450	9.335	1.2488	3.316×10^{-7}
20	8.404	0.0434	0.410	5.202	1.3200	9.657	1.2488	2.573×10^{-7}
30	7.744	0.0434	0.410	4.416	1.5730	9.705	1.2488	2.371×10^{-7}
40	6.864	0.0520	0.422	3.470	1.9720	9.638	1.0851	3.700×10^{-7}
50	6.521	0.0510	0.420	3.132	2.1630	9.600	1.0850	3.840×10^{-7}
60	6.160	0.0526	0.426	2.796	2.4130	9.568	1.0304	4.156×10^{-7}
70	5.632	0.0500	0.426	2.435	2.2980	8.640	1.0850	2.622×10^{-7}
80	5.984	0.0500	0.416	2.577	2.0010	8.456	1.0850	4.178×10^{-7}

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS OF 1mM Cd(II) IN 0.1M NaNO₃ IN THE PRESENCE OF FORMAMIDE AND DIMETHYLFORMAMIDE.

Percentage solvent by Vol.	i_d μA	Slope V	$\frac{-E_{\frac{1}{2}}}{V}$ S.C.E.	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² /sec	η Centipoise	$i_d \eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$	αn_a	$k_{f,h}^0$
<i>Formamide</i>								
0	6.864	0.0305	0.594	8.642	0.8894	6.473	—	—
10	6.336	0.0324	0.610	7.362	0.9429	6.295	—	—
20	5.984	0.0370	0.615	6.567	1.0180	6.045	1.463	5.346×10^{-13}
30	5.280	0.0400	0.681	5.231	1.0710	5.470	1.355	7.178×10^{-14}
40	4.840	0.0455	0.682	4.295	1.1980	5.297	1.190	1.072×10^{-12}
50	4.312	0.0555	0.717	3.410	1.3220	4.943	0.976	1.253×10^{-12}
60	4.136	0.0606	0.724	3.137	1.4030	4.899	0.8943	3.311×10^{-11}
70	3.784	0.0606	0.737	2.626	1.6250	4.808	0.8943	1.590×10^{-11}
80	3.520	0.0412	0.745	2.273	1.9820	4.955	1.3140	3.475×10^{-14}
<i>Dimethylformamide</i>								
0	9.504	0.0313	0.594	6.653	0.8894	8.959	—	—
10	8.888	0.0412	0.596	5.819	1.0900	9.120	1.315	1.278×10^{-11}
20	8.008	0.0412	0.599	4.723	1.3200	9.198	1.315	9.897×10^{-12}
30	7.480	0.0412	0.604	4.121	1.4700	9.067	1.315	7.178×10^{-12}
40	6.336	0.0377	0.608	2.956	1.9210	8.790	1.417	1.161×10^{-12}
50	6.160	0.0370	0.612	2.796	2.0020	8.832	1.456	3.174×10^{-13}
60	5.632	0.0367	0.626	2.336	2.4210	8.567	1.476	1.585×10^{-13}
70	5.368	0.0430	0.639	2.122	2.2960	7.960	1.355	4.864×10^{-13}
80	5.456	0.0454	0.660	2.193	2.0870	9.926	1.190	2.239×10^{-12}

TABLE 3—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS OF 1 mM Tl(I) IN 0.1M NaNO₃ IN THE PRESENCE OF FORMAMIDE AND DIMETHYLFORMAMIDE.

Percentage solvent by Vol.	i_d μ A	Slope V	$-E_t$ V S.C.E.	$D \times 10^5$ cm ² /sec	η centipoise	$i_d \eta^{\dagger}$	αn_a	$k^0_{f,h}$
<i>Formamide</i>								
0	15.2364	0.06102	0.470	6.848	0.9080	14.53	—	—
10	14.9016	0.06842	0.482	6.540	0.9770	14.72	0.7963	8.855×10^{-6}
20	14.5468	0.07142	0.487	6.229	1.0000	14.54	0.76029	2.146×10^{-6}
30	13.4825	0.07142	0.493	5.326	1.1300	12.32	0.76029	1.740×10^{-6}
40	13.1276	0.07142	0.500	5.072	1.189	14.34	0.76029	1.377×10^{-6}
50	12.4180	0.07142	0.501	4.562	1.300	14.16	0.76029	1.268×10^{-6}
60	11.3536	0.07142	0.504	3.796	1.474	13.77	0.76029	1.059×10^{-6}
70	10.6440	0.07142	0.502	3.334	1.832	14.39	0.76029	1.054×10^{-6}
80	10.1180	0.07142	0.493	3.009	2.118	14.77	0.76029	1.309×10^{-6}
<i>Dimethylformamide</i>								
0	15.2564	0.06102	4.470	6.848	0.9080	14.53	—	—
10	14.7840	0.06750	0.466	6.435	1.1020	15.50	0.8029	3.037×10^{-6}
20	13.7280	0.07142	0.463	5.546	1.3180	15.77	0.76029	4.308×10^{-6}
30	11.4400	0.07142	0.458	3.855	1.5850	14.40	0.76029	4.162×10^{-6}
40	10.9120	0.07142	0.457	3.505	1.8710	14.90	0.76029	4.027×10^{-6}
50	10.5600	0.07142	0.451	3.284	2.0500	15.12	0.76029	3.658×10^{-6}
60	9.8560	0.07142	0.450	2.861	2.4040	15.26	0.76029	4.540×10^{-6}
70	8.8000	0.07142	0.442	2.281	2.2960	13.354	0.76029	5.156×10^{-6}
80	9.5040	0.07142	0.432	2.661	2.1300	13.915	0.76029	7.464×10^{-6}

Fig. 5. Electrocapillary curves in the presence of 1 mM Pb²⁺ and 0.1 M NaNO₃ at different percentages of formamide.

Fig. 6. Electrocapillary curves in the presence of 1 mM Pb²⁺ and 0.1 M NaNO₃ at different percentages of dimethylformamide.

increases with the increasing content of formamide. But $i_a\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is not constant so that the change in diffusion coefficient 'D' which ultimately affects i_a , is not solely due to viscosity changes. The varying values of $i_a\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$ suggest that the ion must have suffered a change by solvation⁵.

From aqueous to 70% dimethylformamide, i_a decreases but increases at higher percentage (80%) of dimethylformamide. This is due to the decrease in viscosity at higher percentages of dimethylformamide. This observation is supported by Stokes-Einstein equation :

$$i_a^2\alpha D = kT/6\pi\eta r(x)$$

The $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ of Cd(II), Pb(II) and Tl(I) in aqueous mixtures of formamide and that of Cd(II) and Pb(II) in aqueous mixtures of dimethylformamide is shifted to more negative values. This is indicative of complexation⁶. However, the $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ of Tl(I) in the presence of aqueous mixtures of dimethylformamide is shifted to more positive values. This is explicable on the basis of treatment due to Schaap⁷. In absence of complexation, the equation of Schaap predicts the shift of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ to more positive values. Further, $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ is affected by ion-pair formation in low dielectric constant which is 36.7 for dimethylformamide as compared to 78 for water. The shift takes place as the supporting electrolyte will be less dissociated and a few anions will be available for the ion-pair formation. As the dielectric constant of formamide (109) is higher than that of water, the shift in $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ does not take place to more positive values. These conclusions are borne out by the relationship between $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and dielectric constant of the solvent as given by Born⁸.

A simple qualitative study of electrocapillary curves (Representative Figs. 5 and 6) has been made where drop time (taken as a measure of interfacial tension between mercury and solution) is varied with applied potential. The shape of these electrocapillary curves depends on the nature of the solution and provides information on the equilibrium structure of the double layer and on the capillary activity of dissolved substances. A truncation⁹ of the electrocapillary curve takes place at higher percentages of dimethylformamide (from 50% to 80%). This shows that dimethylformamide acts as a surface active substance at higher percentages.

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